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Comparative Analysis of CNN Architectures in a Federated Learning Environment for Skin Lesion Diagnosis

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning has emerged as a transformative force in the healthcare industry, enabling the development of intelligent systems that support early diagnosis. In particular, deep learning models have shown significant promise in the automated analysis of medical images. Some skin diseases can be malignant, which can lead to serious cancer risks. Therefore, accurate and timely diagnoses play a vital role in preventing the progression of the disease by offering the chance of early intervention. In this study, we focus on skin lesion diagnosis and evaluate the performance of various Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures for accurate and reliable lesion classification. To address privacy concerns associated with centralized data collection, we adopt a federated learning (FL) approach that allows decentralized training across multiple institutions while keeping patient data local. We compare the diagnostic performance of multiple CNN architectures, within the FL framework using benchmark skin lesion datasets. According to the findings, the federated learning-based VGG16 model (FL-VGG16) achieved an accuracy of 83.48%, which is very close to the centralized learning approach. Furthermore, the analysis with the Vanilla CNN architecture shows that the federated learning approach has significantly higher classification performance compared to client-based learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

Medical imaging is a discipline that includes various techniques and methods that enable the visualization of the internal structures of the human body in diagnosis and treatment processes [1]. The use of medical imaging technologies in healthcare services contributes significantly to physicians making more accurate diagnoses and making more effective clinical decisions.

In clinical practice, histopathologic imaging still relies on manual and subjective analysis [2]. However, this approach leads to problems such as pathologist shortage, diagnostic subjectivity, and loss of attention due to the complexity of the images. Therefore, there is a growing need for automated and accurate classification methods. One of the most critical endeavors in the healthcare industry is the diagnosis of cancer through imaging. Cancer is the second most common cause of death worldwide after cardiovascular disease [3]. One of these deadly diseases is skin cancer. Early and

accurate classification of lesions is vital for accurate diagnosis and timely treatment before cancer progresses [4]. However, factors such as unstable and insufficient image data and model adaptability to different domains complicate the automatic classification process.

Today, the field of machine learning has evolved significantly thanks to the increasing volume of data, the complexity of computational processes and the thrilling opportunities offered by its application areas [5]. Deep learning, a sub-branch of machine learning, is a modeling approach that uses multi-layered and multi-feature structures to produce predictive results [6]. Deep learning algorithms stand out with their high accuracy and strong generalization ability, especially in many areas such as image classification, object recognition, voice recognition and segmentation.

CNN is one of the most widely used deep learning models in healthcare. The existing literature indicates that CNN is a highly effective approach for solving many complex problems and especially for the classification of histopathologic images [7]-[9]. Especially with its automatic feature extraction capability, it eliminates the manual pre-processing steps required in traditional methods. In addition, it exhibits superior performance in distinguishing complex tissue structures with high accuracy rates.

Large-scale data is needed to make accurate and reliable diagnoses. Smart health systems have depended on cloud-based centralized artificial intelligence solutions for analyzing health data [10]. However, with the continuous increase in the volume of health data, this centralized structure is losing its efficiency, especially due to delays in the transmission of raw data. Centralized systems are insufficient to meet the increasing network traffic, leading to performance problems. In addition, with the accelerated digitization of medical records and data, the privacy and security of patient information has become a priority [11]. Especially in sensitive healthcare areas such as cancer detection, the protection of patient data is not only a technological requirement, but also a fundamental part of ethical responsibility.

Federated learning is a learning paradigm developed to overcome such challenges [12]. In this system, each client trains the model using its own data in the local environment and only transmits model updates to the central server. Thus, data privacy violations and security risks are significantly reduced by ensuring that the data does not leave the local devices. Federated learning has been successfully applied in many areas where data privacy is critical, such as healthcare [13], finance [14], smart cities [15] and industrial IoT [16].

In this study, CNN-based neural network architectures are used in the federated learning system to classify patient images. The performances of the classification models developed using publicly available skin cancer images are analyzed comparatively.

2 RELATED WORKS

In recent years, rapid advances in the field of deep learning have led to a significant increase in its application areas in the healthcare sector. Especially in areas such as medical image analysis, disease diagnosis, treatment planning, and patient monitoring, the effectiveness of deep learning-based models has increased remarkably, which has significantly improved the accuracy and reliability of clinical decision support systems. In a study, pneumonia and COVID-19 diagnosis was performed using medical images [17]. For this purpose, a transfer learning-based model and a four-layer CNN architecture were used, resulting in 98.42% and 98.34% accuracy rates, respectively. In a study in 2022, 2D MRI brain tumor segmentation was performed using a deep neural network. An f1-score of 0.81 was achieved with the proposed Znet model [18]. In another study, an improved version of the CNN-based LeNet model was proposed for breast cancer diagnosis using ultrasound images [19]. While 85% accuracy was achieved with the standard LeNet model, the accuracy rate increased to 89.91% with the proposed improved LeNet architecture. In another breast cancer diagnosis study, 98% accuracy rate was achieved with CNN optimized with particle swarm optimization metaheuristic

using memography images [20]. [21] applied the pre-trained VGG16 model to lung cancer with a large histopathology dataset.

Federated learning is a new artificial intelligence technology that has attracted increasing attention in recent years due to its advantages in protecting data privacy. Especially in the healthcare industry, it is observed that the use of federated learning framework in applications where patient privacy is critical is rapidly increasing and constitutes a rising trend. A study in 2024 used computed tomography images to diagnose kidney disorders [22]. In this study, a secure approach is presented by using federated transfer learning and CNN architectures as methodology. [23] implemented covid-19 diagnosis with chest x-ray data in a federated learning system. Federated Averaging (FedAvg) was used as a model aggregation technique and was found to have better generalizability compared to personalized FL algorithms. In another federated learning study, classification was performed using Brain Tumor MRI dataset [24]. In the study, a CNN-based structure was used as the local model, and a method was developed in which FedAvg and Federated Proximal (FedProx) algorithms were integrated with a hybrid approach in the model aggregation procedure. It was reported that 97% classification accuracy was achieved with the developed model. Another brain tumor classification study used explainable artificial intelligence with federated learning trained with GoogLeNet [25].

A review of the existing literature reveals that there are various studies on skin cancer diagnosis. In one of these studies, Faster Region-Based CNN method was used for image-based classification [26]. The proposed model achieved an accuracy rate of 86%, while 79% accuracy rate was achieved as a result of manual evaluation of the same test by expert dermatologists. In another study, CNN models were used for benign and malignant skin cancer classification, and while 83.2% accuracy was achieved with vanilla CNN, 85.8% accuracy was reached with InceptionV3 architecture [27]. In a federated learning framework, two different skin cancer datasets were tested separately and combined [28]. Deep CNN architecture was used as the local learning model. With the federated learning approach, 98% accuracy was achieved for one of the datasets and 92% for the other. In the scenario where both datasets were combined, 97% accuracy was achieved. In another study using the federated learning framework, IoT-based sensors were integrated into a skin cancer classification application to develop a system that provides real-time and rapid diagnosis [29].

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Data Collection

In this study, a deep learning-based classification model was developed within the framework of federated learning using images of benign and malignant skin lesions obtained from The International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC) archives. A dataset of 2,637 images was used in the training process, and 660 images (360 benign and 300 malignant) were used as a separate test dataset to test the model. Sample images of benign and malignant skin lesions are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sample images of benign and malignant skin lesions

3.2 CNN Model

CNNs are deep learning models designed specifically for visual data analysis and widely used in areas such as computer vision [30]. They work by using convolutional layers and filters to learn features such as edges, patterns and objects in image data. These layers provide hierarchical feature learning and then capture non-linear structures with activation functions. Pooling layers play a role in dimensionality reduction and highlighting important information. The resulting features are processed with fully connected layers to perform classification tasks. An example of CNN architecture is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: CNN architecture

For skin lotion diagnosis with centralized, client-based and federated learning approaches, we use a basic Vanilla-CNN architecture consisting of three convolution and three pooling layers, working with 128x128 color images. Progressively more complex features are extracted from the image using 32, then 64 and 128 filters in the first convolution layer. In each layer, nonlinearity is added with the ReLU activation function and important features are preserved by reducing the size with max pooling layers. After flattening, a fully connected layer with 128 neurons and 50% dropout is used to prevent overlearning. The final layer is a single neuron with sigmoid activation and this structure was applied for binary classification tasks

In this study, we compare the federated learning framework and pre-trained CNN architectures previously trained on the ImageNet dataset for images with input size 224×224. A transfer learning approach was applied by freezing the convolutional layers of the model. The input data is transferred to the model in 3-channel RGB format and the spatial dimensions are reduced by adding a GlobalAveragePooling2D layer to the output of the base model. Then, a fully connected layer consisting of 128 neurons and a ReLU activation function is used to learn the features in a non-linear manner. In the final layer, binary classification was performed using a single neuron with a sigmoid activation function. The model is trained with mini-batches of 32 samples, which reduces the computational cost and preserves deep feature extraction.

3.3 ResNet50 Architecture

ResNet-50 is a model that stands out among deep convolutional neural network architectures and was developed by [31]. Consisting of 50 layers, this structure was developed to solve the vanishing gradient problem that traditional convolutional networks face as depth increases and adopts the residual learning approach. In this approach, skip connections in each block allow the input information to be transferred directly to the next layers, making the network deeper and facilitating training. The ResNet-50 architecture includes bottleneck blocks, which are a combination of multiple

1×1 , 3×3 and 1×1 convolution layers. In this way, the model keeps the number of parameters under control and provides high accuracy.

3.4 VGG 16

VGG-16 is a deep convolutional neural network architecture developed in 2014 [32]. The Visual Geometry Group (VGG) studied the effect of the depth of convolutional networks on classification accuracy and used small convolution filters. This model consists of 16 weighted layers, 13 convolution layers and 3 fully connected layers. In the VGG-16 architecture, all convolution layers are structured with filters of size 3×3 ; this small filter size allows for a deeper architecture and increases the learning capacity. Each convolution block is followed by a MaxPooling layer of size 2×2 with stride=2.

3.5 DenseNet201 Architecture

DenseNet-201 is a model belonging to the family of Densely Connected Convolutional Networks developed by [33]. In this architecture, each layer has direct access to feature maps from all previous layers; this approach is called "dense connectivity". This structure improves parameter efficiency by reducing feature duplication and allows gradients to propagate effectively to deeper layers. DenseNet-201 consists of 201 layers in total and consists of four dense blocks and transition layers connecting them. Each dense block contains "dense units" configured with 1×1 and 3×3 convolution filters.

3.6 MobileNetV2 Architecture

MobileNetV2 is an enhanced version of MobileNetV1 and is a CNN architecture that aims to enable deep learning models to run efficiently, especially in environments with limited computational resources such as mobile devices and embedded systems [34]. The MobileNetV2 architecture is based on an inverted residual structure in each block. In this structure, shortcut connections are located between linear bottleneck layers within the block. Blocks apply expansion before the input, moving the feature map to a higher dimensional space; on these expanded representations, lightweight depthwise separable convolutions are used for information filtering and extraction. Thus, the model takes advantage of nonlinear transformations while keeping the computational burden to a minimum. MobileNetV2 is a very lightweight model with around 3.4 million learnable parameters.

3.7 EfficientNet-B1 Architecture

EfficientNet-B1 is a highly parametric efficient convolutional neural network architecture belonging to the EfficientNet family developed by [35]. This architecture is designed with the "compound scaling" method, which scales these three dimensions simultaneously and in a balanced manner, instead of scaling width, depth and resolution independently of each other, which is traditionally used during model augmentation. The basic building block of the EfficientNet architecture is the Mobile Inverted Bottleneck Convolution blocks. These blocks are designed similarly to the inverted residual structure used in MobileNetV2 and provide adaptive rescaling of channel-based features through a squeeze-and-excitation mechanism.

3.8 FedAvg Algorithm

The FedAvg algorithm was introduced to the literature in 2017 by [36] as one of the first model aggregation methods proposed in the field of federated learning. This algorithm creates a centralized global model by combining the updated neural network parameters (weights or gradients) trained

locally at each client with a weighted average. This updated global model is sent back to the clients at the end of each round to start a new local learning process, and this cycle continues for a certain number of communication rounds. An example architecture for a federated learning framework is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: An example federated learning architecture [37].

4 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this study, centralized learning, client-based learning and federated learning approaches are compared using CNN-based architectures for skin lesion diagnosis. The performance of the implemented models is evaluated based on micro accuracy, macro accuracy, micro F1-score, and macro F1-score metrics. The performance of the models on the test data is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Performance comparisons of centralized training and federated learning.

Model	Micro Acc	Macro Acc	Micro F1 score	Macro F1 score
Centralized - Vanilla CNN	85.30	85.67	85.30	85.28
Client1 - Vanilla CNN	77.42	79.22	77.42	77.06
Client2 - Vanilla CNN	59.24	55.31	59.24	46.82
FL - Vanilla CNN	80.30	80.25	80.30	80.18
FL - ResNet50	63.18	59.75	63.18	54.74
FL - VGG16	83.48	83.61	83.48	83.42
FL - DenseNet201	82.27	81.36	82.27	81.72
FL - MobileNetV2	80.91	80.61	80.91	80.69
FL - EfficientNetB1	54.55	50.00	54.55	35.29

According to the findings, the centralized Vanilla CNN (CL-Vanilla CNN) model showed the highest performance with a micro accuracy of 85.30%. Among the federated learning approaches, FL-VGG16 and FL-DenseNet201 models achieved 83.48% and 82.27% accuracy rates, respectively. The federated learning approach was found to offer comparable classification performance compared to the centralized learning method. In the comparison based on vanilla CNN architectures, it was observed that the federated learning framework exhibited superior classification performance

compared to client-based learning. For example, while the prediction accuracy of Client 2 was 59%, the same architecture achieved 80% accuracy on the test data with federated learning.

Figure 4: Confusion matrices

Figure 5: Precision-Recall Curves

Confusion matrices of the methods are presented in Figure 4. The classification results show that Client1 predicts the “malignant” class with high accuracy, whereas Client2 is more successful in the “benign” class. This shows that the class labels in the clients are heterogeneously distributed. This imbalance in the data distribution negatively affected the prediction performance of the clients towards the opposite class. In this context, in terms of overall lesion classification performance, federated learning algorithms were found to provide significantly superior results compared to client-based learning approaches. Indeed, using Vanilla CNN for Client2, only 36 out of 300 “malignant” samples were correctly classified, while using the same architecture in a federated learning framework correctly predicted 239 samples.

Precision-Recall (PR) curves of the methods are shown in Figure 5. PR curves are an effective analysis tool for evaluating model performance, especially in classification problems with unbalanced class distribution. Average Precision (AP) metric is obtained by calculating the area under the PR curve. According to the results obtained, the AP value for the centralized learning model CL-Vanilla CNN is 0.91, while this value is 0.90 with the FL-DenseNet201 federated architecture.

The round-based accuracy rates of federated learning-based CNN architectures are presented in Figure 5. Except for the FL-Vanilla CNN model, the other architectures do not show a steady increase in accuracy rates in each round, but rather fluctuations. This shows that in some models, the effect of local updates on the global model may be negative from time to time.

Figure 6: Accuracy versus communication round for federated learning based models

5 CONCLUSION

Federated learning enables collaboration on disease images between different institutions while preserving patient privacy. This allows highly accurate diagnostic models to be developed without centralized data sharing. In this study, centralized training, client-based training and federated learning approaches are compared with CNN-based architectures using skin lesion images. The results show that the federated learning method exhibits a significantly higher classification performance compared to client-based training and achieves accuracy levels close to centralized training.

Federated learning offers significant potential for the development of more inclusive and effective AI models by enabling collaboration between countries' healthcare institutions without violating data privacy. This approach can improve model performance by encouraging collaborative knowledge generation, especially in cases of rare diseases or limited data samples. In this way, information sharing between health systems is strengthened and significant improvements in diagnosis and treatment processes can be achieved on a global scale.

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